

THE EFFECTIVE WAYS OF IMPROVING LANGUAGE SKILLS OF ENGLISH TEACHERS AT SCHOOL

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Abstract. *This scientific article gives information about different methods that can help to develop language skills such as reading, listening, writing and speaking for educators who work at school, several steps to select to teach English language at school. It informs about the difficulties that always prevent teachers being perfect at their field.*

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Lots of teachers know that being really good at English can help them get better jobs and more chances to do exciting things. Today, about one out of every three people in the world (that's around 2 billion people) can speak English. Because of this, it's super important to know: how can teachers get better at speaking English? It can be tricky to figure out the best way to get better at English. This is especially true if you are a busy teacher who has to do many things at once, like grading homework, getting ready for classes, teaching, and taking care of personal stuff, as well. Ascertaining your English proficiency is crucial before beginning any learning task. Finding activities at the appropriate level requires knowing where to begin. It goes without saying that attempting tasks that are excessively challenging might be discouraging, and working only within your area of expertise will not advance you. You can take an exam to determine your English proficiency. You can then select the appropriate practice exercises for your desired level based on the results. Watching movies in English can be an enjoyable, practical, and useful method of increasing your exposure to the language.

You can watch movies with English audio and subtitles in your native tongue if it looks a little intimidating. When you're ready, switch to English audio and subtitles. Watching movies is also an excellent method to sharpen your listening abilities because different languages and accents are frequently employed. Additionally, it will assist you in growing your vocabulary of colloquial terms and phrases that are used on a daily basis by local speakers.

Select a book (from children's to adult) based on your level of English. Additionally, books with side-by-side translations are available for purchase. Reading a book that you have previously read in your native tongue is an additional option. It will be easy to follow since you will already be aware of what happens in this scenario.

Enjoying music is another fantastic and enjoyable method to get better at speaking English. Fortunately, you can read the lyrics along with the song and find them simply online. When you encounter unfamiliar terms, you should look them up in a dictionary and make a note of their definition. It is essential to select music based on your skill level in order to prevent frustration: slower songs with simpler lyrics for beginners or faster songs with more complex lyrics for intermediate or advanced learners.[1]

During the day, when you have limited time, like when traveling by train or bus from home to work or vice versa, using apps on your smartphone or tablet can be quite convenient and quick. But picking the best app could be challenging because there are so many of them out there. Here,

I suggest four apps that we believe could be useful: With the media-based app Fluent U, you may view English-language videos for news, music, and advertisements. You can tap the interactive captions to learn more about specific terms; With the help of customizable program called Duolingo, users can learn languages while having fun. To advance to new levels and unlock upgrades, users must complete brief courses in order to earn coins. Furthermore, there is a bulletin board where students engage and support one another; With the help of the Hello Talk app, English language learners may chat with native speakers. You can use text, audio recording, phone call, video call, and even drawings to communicate with English speakers anywhere in the world. You can also get feedback from the community by posing questions to them; This app is intended for intermediate English language learners. The first exam that users take will decide the difficulty of your English lessons. With the help of this software, you may learn English through gaming, watching videos, and taking audiobooks.

Most teachers always doubt about selecting the methods to teach. They have enough knowledge, but they do not have appropriate method to use. Here some steps that can absolutely help educators to select methods.

Learning Objectives

When you're planning a lesson, it's important to think about what you want your students to learn. Have you thought about what you want them to remember from the lesson? The goals for the class should match the rules and guidelines for what they need to learn. It's best to make these goals clear and specific, so everyone knows what to aim for. You might need to use different teaching methods to help your students understand the material, especially if it's complicated or covers a lot of information.

Learning styles

Pupils' favored learning preferences should be your second consideration when creating a lesson plan. Learners have varying preferred approaches to assimilating and retaining information, referred to as learning preferences. These techniques can be seen, heard, felt, or spoken.

Educational setting

Students' learning environments are the third factor you should consider when deciding on a course of study. The classroom, online platform, group size, noise level, available resources, emotional state and other physical, social and psychological aspects of learning, it is all part of the learning environment.

Criticism for growth

The learning feedback you give your pupils is the fourth consideration when picking a teaching style. Whether in grades, comments, suggestions, or praise, learning feedback informs students of their progress and performance.

Results of learning

The desired results in scholarly learning should be the last attention when determining instructional strategies. By giving up on a session or direction, your pupils should have acquired unique know-how, competencies, attitudes, and behaviors, referred to as getting to know results.

Almost all language teachers have some difficulties to deliver the knowledge to students or it is sometimes difficult even to learn language itself. It is believed that it has some reasons.

Languages are complicated

Teaching any language, educators often in need of having native speaker fluency, but that's usually not enough to do the job. It's absolutely important that teachers also comprehend the

grammatical structures that underpin all languages – this part of the job is frequently ignored and underappreciated but it's essential for classroom success. After all, if you don't have knowledge about the difference between an adjective and an adverb or cannot provide examples of countable and uncountable English nouns if you are teaching English language, then how can you hope to explain key concepts to students? **Teaching language is not an easy task.** Keeping your students engaged, interested and stimulated in their learning day in and day out can be a challenge. Especially in formal education settings (like in primary school or secondary education) where students often don't have any choice about attending. Educators will frequently find themselves teaching different subjects to different classes across different age groups (read also our dedicated post about teaching languages to different age group). All of which require a bespoke lesson plan using a variety of stimulus to work through – teachers therefore need to be highly organized, detail-focused, creative, resilient (I could go on!) to succeed. Creating lesson plans, marking papers, writing reports and doing all of the other student analysis required is also very time-consuming. It's important for language teachers to keep focus on language learning outcomes and to ensure that this administrative work does not take up too much of their free time. In order to teach effectively, you should have some features, such as managing classroom, supporting your learners, handling parents and others.[2]

Certainly, a key challenge for all teachers is ensuring that all students stay on task and work in a calm and orderly manner. Yet in every language classroom and in all schools, there're always someone who seems determined to make life as difficult as possible for the teachers. Handling those students can take skill and experience.

For language educators teaching their native language overseas, this does present real challenges. Just imagine that you're trying to engage a 14-year old who is refusing to participate in your Spanish class and she's talking to you in her mother tongue which you don't understand. How would you respond to ensure that her behavior doesn't distract the rest of the class? Remember to check out our other post for further tips on classroom management! All teachers should support their students. Ultimately, the role of the language teacher is to help students develop their fluency and comprehension, so working with individual students' needs can present a wide range of challenges. Although teaching in higher education or teaching adults can be hugely satisfying as you help them achieve their life objectives, the classroom environment can often be serious and overly goal-oriented. This puts additional pressure on teachers as they expect top-quality teaching class after class to get the grades they need.

On the other hand, teaching students in primary school usually means more time spent on behavior management, more time spent building basic language skills and certainly more time spent developing engaging lesson plans and resources. And of course, there's parents to deal with too many language schools are privately owned enterprises with affluent, picky clients. In addition to meeting or surpassing anticipated progress, parents want to make sure their kids are receiving the greatest education available. For both students and teachers, parents can consequently be a frequent and occasionally unwanted presence in the classroom. Therefore, it is vital to establish clear boundaries and cultivate a good rapport and communication with parents. It's crucial to thoroughly investigate the culture of the nation or area you're teaching in if you're teaching abroad. Although every parent is unique, being culturally sensitive can help you prevent inadvertently upsetting someone and creating a serious diplomatic crisis.

The teacher is in command in the classroom. You establish the lesson plan, supervise the pupils under your supervision, present the learning objectives, and manage the classroom setting. As a result, every time a language instructor enters their classroom, they bear a great deal of responsibility. The greatest educators view this as a special opportunity and a privilege, but it is not for everyone.

Many language teachers take advantage of the chance to travel and experience other regions of the world. The school may not have all of the educational resources or technology (such as apps, broadband, laptops, textbooks, etc.) that you are accustomed to depending on where you wind up. Naturally, this can be shocking, and it makes teachers reconsider the resources they have at their disposal as well as the approaches they can take to teaching languages. Other environments could provide teachers with a rigid curriculum, work plans, and tools that they must utilize. If you're accustomed to using your imagination to create things specifically for each class, this kind of setting can also showcase its own educators.

It's critical to have backup and assistance when needed, no matter where you teach. Building a network of peers with whom you collaborate is crucial since teaching a new and foreign language to a room full of strangers can be challenging. Sharing teaching materials, career development advice, student perspectives, and, of course, socializing are all examples of this. It's critical that your department head and school administration are on hand to assist and support you in the event that issues with parents or kids develop.

In the classroom, things don't always go as planned, as any teacher who has ever taught knows! The photocopier is damaged, the WiFi isn't functioning at its best, the computers aren't working, and everything can—and often does—go wrong while working with kids! Because of this, being a language teacher may be quite stressful, and you can't always be in complete control of everything. This is one of the biggest problems that language teachers have; the only thing you can do is learn how to react fast and humorously, try to make the most of every circumstance, and always, always have a backup plan!

For many language teachers, the chance to travel and explore the world is one of the main appeals of the job. However, relocating to a different country to live and work can be tough. It's hard to be away from your comfort zone, especially if you don't know the local language. Plus, there's always a lot to quickly learn about: the new school, new coworkers, new students, traditions, weather, transportation, and more. Culture shock is real and can be a big challenge for educators teaching internationally, so take time to familiarize yourself with your new surroundings before getting started. Knowing a little of the local scene can also really help to engage students. And no-one wants to start a new job whilst shaking off jet lag! BUT despite the challenges outlined above, it is worth repeating that being a language teacher is a hugely rewarding job that genuinely helps transform the lives of your students. It can be a great way to experience a new culture and possibly to learn a new language of your own. It's full of personal development opportunities and enables you to meet, teach and learn from a wide range of people.[3] English, always regarded as a global lingua franca, is an important skill set in today's contemporary world. It opens doors for communication, educational opportunities, and professional development. But, achieving proficiency, particularly in writing, can sometimes be a difficult task.

1. Comprehending the Basics

Before you can write well, you must comprehend the essentials of English grammar and syntax. Knowing parts of speech, sentence structure, punctuation, and verb tenses can greatly

enhance your written English. There are countless resources available online, including grammar guides, such as Grammarly, and synonyms websites such as Power The Saurus.

2. Widen Your Vocabulary

Expanding your vocabulary can add color and precision to your writing. Try to learn by heart new words daily and practice utilizing them in sentences. You can do this through reading, using apps like Anki, or websites like Vocabulary.com. Remember, the aim is not to use complex words unnecessarily, but to improve your ability to express your thoughts accurately.

3. Read permanently

Reading exposes you to various writing styles, tones, vocabulary, and sentence structures, developing your understanding and utilization of English. This could be anything from novels and newspapers to scientific journals or blogs, depending on your interest. According to Krashen, extensive reading can significantly improve vocabulary acquisition and improve overall writing competence.[4]

4. Write permanently

As the saying goes, “practice makes perfect”. Regularly practicing writing can greatly improve your skills. Start a journal, write stories, or summarize articles in your own words. Don’t be afraid to make mistakes; they are stepping stones to mastery. Feedback on your writing is crucial in this process, so consider using platforms like Lang Correct where native speakers can review and correct your compositions.

5. Use Online Instruments

Leverage technology to polish your writing skills. Tools like Grammarly and Hemingway Editor can check your grammar, punctuation, spelling, and readability. These can be excellent for immediate, automated feedback, allowing you to learn from your mistakes and avoid them in the future.

6. Take a Course or Join a Workshop

There are numerous online courses aimed at enhancing English writing skills. Platforms like Coursera and edX offer courses from universities worldwide, covering various aspects of English writing. You can also become a student at Speak Now and learn in a personalized way for your necessities. Workshops and webinars are also great opportunities to learn new techniques and gain feedback on your writing.[5]

7. Proofread and Edit

Proofreading is a critical step in the writing process that’s often overlooked. Always review your writing for any mistakes or areas of improvement. You’ll be surprised how much your writing can improve from one draft to the next. Consider using proofreading symbols and strategies to make this process more systematic

8. Write with aim

Always have a clear goal for what you want to communicate in your writing. It could be to inform, persuade, narrate, or describe. Knowing your objective can guide the style and structure of your writing.[6]

9. Be Tolerant and Persistent

Improving English writing skills is a marathon, not a sprint. It requires patience, tolerance, and a lot of practice. Keep the end goal in sight and celebrate small victories along the way.

Being a teacher demands not only having really good speaking and writing skills, but also reading and listening skills. Writing and speaking are considered as productive skills while reading

and listening can be developed by practicing permanently. So, it will be easy for teachers to develop their listening skills by practicing it every day.[7] Maintain the reading activities, whether it is material for which you have the audio or not. Reading is a powerful way to enhance vocabulary. Besides, when we read in a foreign language, we usually subvocalize, in other words we make the sounds in our heads. If possible, try to find content that has matching audio and text files so you can search for missing words or phrases. It's not required, but it's helpful. However, don't stop there. It's not always possible to find such material, so when reading and listening, use different sources: a newspaper article here, a podcast or an interview there.

Try to stick to a narrow range of topics, such as current events or politics, that cover roughly the same vocabulary.[8]

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